

RESISTANCE INDICATORS OF WHEAT AND RICE VARIETIES TO FUSARIUM WILT IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *In the given article wheat and rice varieties grown in the republic that are resistant to fusarium are studied. The research studied the resistance of wheat varieties Alekseich, Asr, Vekha, Grom, Krasnodar-99, Kroshka, Tanya, Zimnitsa, Yuka to diseases. Among these varieties, Asr and Zimnitsa varieties are resistant to fusarium wilt. The level of resistance to diseases of rice varieties Iskandar, Sadaf, Laser, Tarona, Tantana was studied in experiments and it was found that the Laser and Tantana varieties are resistant to fusarium wilt.*

Keywords: *rice, wheat, fungus, disease, fusarium, variety, Alekseich, Asr, Vekha, Grom, Krasnodar-99, Kroshka, Tanya, Zimnitsa, Yuka, Iskandar, Sadaf, Laser, Tarona, Tantana, Fusarium.*

It is important to suggest that the most cost-effective and environmentally friendly method of combating diseases caused by microorganisms is the method of breeding disease-resistant varieties. There are no varieties of grain crops with pronounced resistance to Fusarium wilt, but depending on the level of resistance, there may be differences in relation to the pathogen between varieties. (Senröder, Christenson, 1963; Snyders, 1990). Since the degree of resistance of varieties to diseases depends on external environmental factors, dependence on conditions is a relative concept.

Resistance of wheat to Fusarium head blight is specialized and is not considered a hereditary trait of the variety. Therefore, some varieties exhibit high resistance to Fusarium head blight, while other varieties may not exhibit it at all. Because there is no genetic correlation in the interaction of the plant and the pathogen. As a result, in some places Fusarium head blight is common, and in other places, depending on the source of infection, the disease does not occur at all. Therefore, the spread of the disease does not depend on the resistance of the plant, but depends on the rate of spread of induction. Fusarium head blight of wheat on the ground is divided into the following unrelated groups: I - resistance to pathogen penetration; II - resistance to pathogen spread along the ear; III - grain resistance to pathogen damage; IV – tolerance, V - varieties that accumulate or decompose mycotoxins. (Schroeder, Christenson, 1963; Mesterhazy, 2002; Boutigny et al., 2008). Since the level of resistance detected in wheat is controlled independently, a comparative study of various genotype indicators is necessary for complete control of the resistance level. Despite the fact that the resistance of wheat and rice to fusarium head blight is genetically multicomponent, cobs of varieties with high resistance to the disease are less infected and accumulate a smaller amount of mycotoxin. In resistant varieties, this indicator is characterized by abundance.

The Krasnodar Research Institute of Agriculture of Russia has studied the fusarium resistance of wheat, barley and rice from grain crops and created relatively fusarium-resistant

varieties: Batko, Daka, Delta, Deya, Krasnodar-6, Pamyat, Starshina (Rybalkintal), 2000; Koleskinov et al., 2001; Avlova, 2008).

According to I.B. Ablova (2008), when the fusarium-resistant Delta variety is infected with a suspension of the fungus *F.graminearum*, the disease reduces the yield by 7.90%, while the disease-resistant Kipova variety loses 20.30% of the yield.

The issue of wheat resistance to fusarium is being clarified by employees of the regional branch of the North-East Research Institute of Agriculture (Shemigova, 2005; Shemigova, Kharina, 2008). As a result of studies conducted on artificial and natural infectious backgrounds, it was established that among the varieties resistant to fusarium: Vyatskiy, Argamak, Astor.

Wheat varieties grown in European countries are moderately resistant to fusarium wilt, and durum wheat varieties are resistant to the disease (Ablova, Gritsay, 2001; Snyders, 1990; Buerstmayrtal, 1996; Mestergazi, 1997).

In the conditions of the republic, the incidence of fusarium in wheat and rice, provided that the root system, then the stem, then the leaf and, finally, the ear, exhibit vertical resistance depending on the level of resistance of existing plants. Zoned varieties, the intensity of fusarium manifestation and the resistance of varieties according to the following V-point scale can be assessed using

- 0 points - no symptoms of the disease are observed in the root, stem and leaf of the plant.
- Grade I – the color of the grass roots changes from the inside to dark brown and rots, and the yield decreases by 2-3 centners.
- Grade II – the plant stem has become thinner, and the joints and articulations have become darker. The yield has decreased by 4-6 centners.
- Grade III – the diseased plant has a disturbed water balance, the leaves wither and turn yellow. The yield has decreased by 7-9 centners.
- Grade IV – the plant lags in growth, does not collect, the ears are discolored and consist of small, underdeveloped grains. The yield has decreased by more than 10 centners.

The data obtained on the basis of generalization of resistance of disease symptoms to fusarium of wheat and rice varieties grown in the conditions of central and some southern regions of Uzbekistan in field conditions during different periods of vegetation is presented in this table. The studies were conducted on 10 main varieties widely grown in the republic.

Degree of resistance of wheat varieties to fusarium

Number	Variety name	Disease incidence, in points				
		0	I	II	III	IV
1	Alekseich			+		
2	Asr					+
3	Vekha				+	
4	Grom			+		
5	Krasnodar-99				+	
6	Kroshka			+		
7	Tanya			+		
8	Zimnitsa					+

9	Yuka			+		
10	Gazgon			+		

As it can be seen from the table, the manifestation of resistance to diseases in the central and southern regions of the republic is different for local and imported varieties from Russia. None of the 10 varieties studied in the study demonstrates complete immunity to fusarium.

It has not been established that the studied varieties were not affected by the disease at all. Depending on the soil and climatic conditions of the studied areas, from grass shoots to crop ripening after sowing seeds, fusarium has different infection rates in different phases of vegetation. But it was noted that some varieties exhibit resistance to fusarium. In the course of the research, rice varieties resistant to fusarium were studied. Experiments were conducted on 5 varieties, widespread in the southern and central regions.

Resistance level of rice varieties to fusarium

Number	Variety name	Incidence level, in points				
		0	I	II	III	IV
1	Iskander		+			
2	Sadaf		+			
3	Lazer				+	
4	Tarona			+		
5	Tantana				+	

According to the table, the resistance of 5 rice varieties to fusarium was studied, planted in the conditions of the Syrdarya region from the central region of the republic and grown in the conditions of the Surkhandarya region from the southern region. It turned out that there are relatively resistant varieties. The varieties resistant to fusarium wilt include Iskandar and Sadaf. In conclusion, when studying the varieties of wheat and rice resistant to fusarium, it was found that out of 10 wheat varieties, the Alekseich, Grom, Kroshka, Tanya, Yuka, Gozgon varieties were resistant to fusarium when studied under natural conditions. While studying the natural resistance to fusarium in a total of 5 rice varieties, the Iskandar and Sadaf varieties turned out to be more resistant than other varieties. The republic does not grow varieties of wheat and rice that are completely resistant to fusarium, but there are varieties that are resistant to some diseases.

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